

Project RASHealth: Water disinfection strategies to improve Atlantic salmon parr production in freshwater recirculating aquaculture systems

Deliverable 3.2

PAA and O3 administration to control a *Y. ruckeri* outbreak in RAS

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Background

Norwegian parr industry faces disease outbreaks causing high production losses and threatening the use of RAS. There is an urgent need for effective and operational water disinfection strategy.

RASHealth ambition: To develop new water treatment practices for Atlantic salmon parr in freshwater RAS using O₃ or PAA.

Background

Task 3.2 Benchmark study on PAA and O₃ administration to control a *Y. ruckeri* outbreak in Atlantic salmon parr FW-RAS and fish welfare indicators assessment

Aim: To determine the PAA concentration and administration in which no negative consequences are observed in Atlantic salmon parr performance (**SO3**).

Graphic abstract

Goal:

Developing effective disinfection strategies to limit disease outbreaks in RAS

Methods:

Evaluate PAA and ozone use during *Y.ruckeri* challenge - 4 week trial with Atlantic salmon parr in FW-RAS

Outcome:

Infection prevalence +

Control
33% 13% 7%

Clinical sign: Enlarged spleen

Health and welfare

PAA and ozone → no significant effect on growth, health and welfare of Atlantic salmon in trial

Water quality

Turbidity: Ozone < PAA < Control
Nitrite: Control < Ozone < PAA - potential negative effect on biofilter

Control PAA O₃

Material and Methods

Fish: Atlantic salmon parr (± 19 g; N=1800)

Systems: 9 RAS, fish tank volume 500L

Treatments:

- 1) Semi-continuous PAA administration in three RAS (target of 1 mg/L PAA),
- 2) Continuous O₃ application in three other RAS (target of 300-350 mV), and
- 3) Control groups with no disinfection in the last three units

Figure 1: A sketch of the nine RAS, including what treatments they will be exposed to.

Material and Methods

Figure 2: Shows timeline of the experiment, with specific events highlighted. The timeline is separated into three periods: acclimatization to RAS, acclimatization to ozone and PAA, and pathogen challenge.

Material and Methods

Sampling and Analysis

Figure 3: Show an overview of the trial, what water quality parameters will be measured, and what samplings, analysis and observation from fish will be taken.

Results

Fish performance

The mortality throughout the experiment was minimal, with a total of 5 fish dead, representing all treatments.

There were no statistical differences among treatments for TGC, SGR or K-factor.

Figure 4: Bar chart which shows growth parameters; TGC, SGR (%/d), final K-factor for control, PAA and ozone treatment, presented as mean \pm SD for each treatment group.

Results

Detection of *Y. ruckeri*

Table 1: In total 45 spleen samples were sent (n= 15 per treatment) for qPCR detection of Y. ruckeri at the end of the trial. The percentage of positive samples per treatment group are described as average prevalence of positive samples \pm SD. One way ANOVA test results shown for % positive samples (arcsine-transformed).

	Control	PAA	Ozone	P-value (ANOVA)
n total	15	15	15	-
Total positives	5	2	1	-
% positive	33.3% \pm 30.6	13.3% \pm 11.5	6.7% \pm 11.5	0.469

Results

External fish welfare

Figure 5: Radial chart showing the mean scores of each external welfare indicator before treatment had started (day 0) in A), and B) 29 days after treatment with ozone and PAA + 20 days since *Y. ruckeri* was added to all systems (day 29).

Results

Clinical sign scoring

Figure 6: Bar chart that represents average prevalence \pm SD (y-axis) of the clinical signs; exophthalmia, enlarged spleen, external hemorrhage, ascites, and hemorrhage in inner organs, observed in $n=15$ fish per treatment (control, ozone and PAA), on the last sampling (day 29).

Results

Histological evaluation

Figure 7: Bar chart of the prevalence of gill scores (y-axis) for each treatment group (control, ozone and PAA), within each of the five sampling points (x-axis), based on evaluating histology gill sections.

Figure 8: Bar chart with average prevalence of different gill alterations (y-axis) observed in gill histology sections on the last sampling day: hyperplasia, hypertrophy, fusion, oedema, and necrosis, including healthy gill lamellae in control, PAA and ozone treatment.

Results

Glucose, lactate, and hematocrit in plasma

Figure 9: Graph showing changes in plasma lactate (A), glucose (B) and hematocrit (C) in the five sampling points in the trial for control, PAA and ozone group.

Results

Water quality

Table 2: A summary of the average values of specific water quality parameters per treatment from day 0 (ozone and PAA treatments started) to day 28 (a day before trial ended), taken from fish tank outlet.

Parameters	Control	PAA	Ozone	P-value (ANOVA)
O₂ (% saturation)	98.6 ± 1.9	104.3 ± 4.2	103.7 ± 5.8	0.272
Temperature (°C)	11.5 ± 0.1	11.5 ± 0.1	11.5 ± 0.1	0.710
CO₂ (mg/L)	3 ± 0	3 ± 0	3 ± 0	.
pH	7.42 ± 0.08	7.38 ± 0.16	7.45 ± 0.01	0.724
Turbidity (ntu)	8.13 ± 2.65 ^a	3.60 ± 0.68 ^b	1.02 ± 0.31 ^c	<0.001 *
UVT (%)	48.4 ± 2.8 ^a	54.9 ± 3.4 ^a	75.4 ± 2.5 ^b	<0.001 *
Redox tank outlet (mV)	218.6 ± 5.2	219.4 ± 3.0	233.9 ± 19.7	0.281
PAA (mg/L)	.	0.09 ± 0.02	.	.
Ozone (mg Cl₂/L)	.	.	0.03 ± 0.00	.
NH₄⁺-N (mg/L)	0.38 ± 0.06	0.40 ± 0.08	0.47 ± 0.04	0.257
NH₃-N (µg/L)	2.19 ± 0.76	2.03 ± 0.69	2.79 ± 0.29	0.346
NO₂-N (mg/L)	0.23 ± 0.02 ^a	0.34 ± 0.02 ^b	0.27 ± 0.03 ^a	0.003 *
NO₃-N (mg/L)	28.8 ± 1.9	25.8 ± 3.2	29.9 ± 0.8	0.145

Results

Water quality

Figure 11: Fish tanks with different treatments on the last day of the trial. A) is the control treatment, B) is PAA treatment and C) is ozone treatment.

Figure 10: Graph shows the average turbidity (ntu) measured against days for the three treatments; control, PAA, and ozone ($n = 3$) in water samples taken from fish tank outlet.

Discussion

Impact of PAA and ozone on Y. ruckeri infection

In the present study there was minimal mortality for all treatment groups and observations of clinical signs, behavioral signs, and external welfare indicators did not indicate that fish were acutely sick. A full-scale acute ERM outbreak was therefore not achieved. Because of this the full potential of ozone or PAA as disinfectants in the water affect an ERM disease outbreak could not be investigated to a full extent.

Impact of PAA and ozone on growth, fish health and welfare after *Y. ruckeri* challenge

PAA and ozone disinfection did not significantly affect growth of Atlantic salmon in the present trial.

Similarly, to mortality and growth, the external welfare of fish was also not significantly impacted by the pathogen challenge

The only clinical sign with significant difference between treatments was enlarged spleen, where ozone group had significantly lower prevalence of this observation than control group. Based on the function of the spleen, these findings together with the detection of *Y. ruckeri* in the spleen indicates less of an immune response in Atlantic salmon exposed to ozone, compared to non-exposed fish, which is likely because the ozonated fish had lower prevalence of infection than control group.

Discussion

Impact of PAA and ozone on water quality

Most water quality parameters, including oxygen, temperature, CO₂, pH, redox, NH₄⁺-N, NH₃-N and NO₃-N did not seem to be impacted by PAA and ozone treatment during the trial.

The parameters affected were the transparency of water with the measurement of turbidity (ntu), UVT (%), and NO₂-N.

Conclusion

The goal of this study was primarily to evaluate if Atlantic salmon parr continuously exposed to ozone or PAA in RAS could prevent a disease outbreak of ERM. It was established that the two disinfectants could not prevent fish from getting infected with *Y. ruckeri*, as indicated by the positive detection of the pathogen in spleen and mild clinical signs as enlarges spleen and hemorrhages observed in all treatments. Some positive trends were detected in the ozone and PAA treatment groups, as the prevalence of infection being lower in both PAA and ozone compared to control group, however with no significant differences.

It could be suggested that control group showed a stronger immune response in the spleen with significantly more fish registering enlarged spleen than in the ozone group. PAA group also registered less enlarged spleen than control but was not significantly affected. These trends could suggest a lower *Y. ruckeri* load in the water of PAA and ozone treated RAS. It's therefore recommended that future studies try to explore this further by inducing a significant ERM outbreak with mortalities, to see if bigger contrasts could be made between the treatments.

Conclusion

It was established during the trial that continuous ozone (233.9 mV in fish tank outlet) and PAA exposure (0.09 mg/L PAA in fish tank outlet) did not significantly affect health and welfare of Atlantic salmon parr in RAS, as external welfare indicators, growth, stress parameters and gill histological evaluation showed no significant differences between groups. Gill lesions such as hyperplasia and hypertrophy were however more prevalent in PAA group, which could suggest gills are sensitive to this compound even at low concentrations.

PAA and ozone treatment did affect some water quality parameters. Turbidity and UVT were highly affected by ozone, and to some extent PAA, which indicate less larger particles in the water. Furthermore, PAA in the doses added may have influenced the nitrite-oxidating bacterial community in the biofilter as nitrite-N was significantly higher in RAS with PAA than in control and ozone RAS. pH, oxygen, carbon dioxide, ammonium, ammonia, and nitrate levels were not significantly affected by ozone or PAA exposure in RAS.

The work from this study could be valuable for developing effective disinfection protocols in RAS to eliminate pathogens without negatively affected fish health and welfare, while still maintaining good water quality and biofilter performance.

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